

Justice and Development Party (PJD), Morocco

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Entry tags: Reform Movement, Religious Group, Arabic, Language, Nationalism, North African Religion, Islamic Traditions, Maghreb Religions

Also known as the *Partie de Justice et Development* (PJD), or *Hizb al-'Adala wal-Tanmiya* in Arabic. Known as Morocco's "moderate" Islamist party, which for elections first in 1998, made steady gains, then lost badly in 2021 elections, but are still politically active. Worth noting: the PJD is technically *only* the name of the political party (which contends in Moroccan elections), while the broader (and older) social movement/organization which they draw on (ideologically, and for political candidates) is the Movement of Unity and Reform (MUR). I have tried to connect and/or distinguish the two whenever necessary in comments below.

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Morocco

Region tags: Northern Africa, Africa, Morocco

Morocco

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Malika Zeghal, *Islamism in Morocco: Religion, Authoritarianism, and Electoral Politics*. Translated by George Holoch. Princeton, NJ: Markus Wiener, 2008.
- Source 2: Zakia Salime, "Embedded Counterpublics: Women and Islamic Revival in Morocco" 37, no. 3 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1353/fro.2016.a634362>
- Source 3: Malika Zeghal, "On the Politics of Sainthood: Resistance and Mimicry in Postcolonial Morocco." *Critical Inquiry* 35, no. 3 (2009): 587–610. <https://doi.org/10.1086/600093>

Reference: Benkirane, Abdelillah. *Al-haraka Al-islamiya Wa Ishkaliyat Al-manhaj [the Islamist Movement and the Problematic of Methodology]*. Casablanca: Manshourat al-Forqan, 1999.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://carnegieendowment.org/2017/12/28/morocco-s-islamist-party-redefining-politics-under-pressure-pub-75121>
- Source 1 Description: Intissar Fakir, "Morocco's Islamist Party: Redefining Politics Under Pressure." Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, 2017.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Morocco_Spiegel-FINAL.pdf

– Source 2 Description: Avi Spiegel, "Succeeding by Surviving: Examining the Durability of Political Islam in Morocco: Working Paper." Brookings Institution, 2015.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.pjd.ma>

– Source 1 Description: Official Justice and Development Party Website (in Arabic)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: People born to Muslim parents are generally considered Muslim by default, but this does not extend to PJD membership specifically

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Not "assigned" by class, however, the PJD is noted to be most popular among literate, urbanite upper-middle class Moroccan Muslims

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– I don't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Voting

Notes: Although voting in parliamentary elections does not constitute "membership" in the PJD, voting for PJD candidates of course does signal some endorsement of their policies, and electoral participation in general makes them unique compared to other Islamist parties in Morocco

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: The PJD itself does not "proselytize" per se. However, those who are formally committed to the Movement for Unity and Reform (MUR), the civil society movement that the PJD grows out of, are more or less expected to engage in da'wa, meaning the practice of "calling" less pious Muslims to engage more fervently in religious practice and adhere to Islamic social norms.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: See above; the practice of da'wa is more or less expected of all adherents to the movement, not just those in the PJD's official political ranks.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: If by "missionary work" the intention is proselytization outside of Morocco. The MUR and PJD operate on primarily local and national levels.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– I don't know

Notes: Rarely is violence used to coerce followers. However, Da'wa can be highly socially coercive.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Politicians of the PJD who win and hold parliamentary seats are paid by the Moroccan government. Other candidates and other members of the MUR (the PJD's social arm) are paid out of private funds of the movement.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The MUR raises private funds to support its own religious infrastructure. However, the PJD and Moroccan monarchy are broadly aligned on many religious issues, so state-funded media infrastructures and government bodies disseminate many ideas that would appeal to PJD and MUR members.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The Moroccan King is not considered the figurehead of Islam, writ large. He does, however, present himself as the highest religious authority *in Morocco* by claiming the title "Commander of the Faithful" (amir al-mu'minin) and the leadership of the PJD and MUR by and large recognize this.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: In fact, PJD electoral participation is predicated on several clear, government-mandated boundaries between religious and political activity. The PJD cannot, for example, run political candidates who hold another "religious" office (such as an imam) and cannot use "religious"

spaces (like mosques) for recruitment or other operations.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Notes: The exception is Morocco's Personal Status Code, known as the *mudawwana*, which concerns matters of family law such as marriage, divorce, and inheritance, and which is ostensibly based the precedent of the Maliki legal school of Sunni Islam.

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– I don't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: There is a concept of apostasy (*ridda*) in Islam, generally, but as of 2022 legal prosecution of apostasy in Morocco was more or less banned, and extremely rare prior to that.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Like many other Islamists, the MUR and PJD refer to the Qur'an and Hadith as a source of law; or, more accurately, as the "limits" (hudud) of any sort of progressive legal reform.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an was originally revealed and circulated in oral form, and its recitation is still venerated by pious Muslims, members of the PJD or MUR, and otherwise.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an is believed to be the unadulterated Word of God

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: The Hadith are reported actions and sayings of the Prophet Muhammad, thought to be an exemplar of human conduct

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– I don't know

Notes: Morocco has numerous religious monuments, especially of a historical nature, but none specific to the PJD or MUR itself.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Many mosques (see below) have large, associated courtyard spaces which accommodate overflow during canonical prayer.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Mosques, madrasas (institutions of Islamic higher education)

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Notes: Certain schools of Islamic theology and philosophy posit a spirit/body distinction, but such ideas are rarely engaged by the MUR or PJD, whose ideologies are concerned primarily with legal and ethical matters

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

As cenotaphs:

– No

In cemetery:

– Yes

Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: See notes

Notes: God has 99 names, each expressing a character quality

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The Qur'an

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Since PJD ideology is a somewhat "secularized" version of Sunni Islamic orthodoxy, in the sense that it treats primarily economic and social issues, not theology per se, answers here will address only

those issues where God and divine authority seem to be "present" in that ideology specifically

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– No

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:
– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes

Notes: Although things like divination practices, writing of charms, etc. have long histories in Islamic societies, and Morocco especially, Islamists tend to be against sorcery (sihr) as either a form of idolatry (shirk) or as an innovation of doctrine (bid'a)

Reference: Spadola, Emilio. *The Calls of Islam: Sufis, Islamists, and Mass Mediation in Urban Morocco*. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press, 2014.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Certain members of the MUR, PJD, or other (related) Moroccan Islamists may have occasionally made mention in the past of God "punishing" Morocco (or Moroccans) for unfavorable political acts (e.g. relations with Israel or imperialist governments) but that seems to have faded from public discussion

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: See note above

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is in fact the original historical basis of the PJD, whose social movement predecessor the

Movement for Unity and Reform (MUR) basically coalesced out of a desperate set of groups working to Islamize society "from below." This included especially proscription of conservative, Islamic social norms, like pious dress (headscarf for women), separation of genders at social gatherings, and consumption of halal goods and culture.

Reference: Salime, Zakia. "Embedded Counterpublics: Women and Islamic Revival in Morocco" 37, no. 3 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1353/fro.2016.a634362>.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence from pre-marital sex and adultery are widely accepted norms for both males and females amongst most of the MUR and PJD's pious Muslim membership

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence from pre-marital sex (see above)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Not mandated by the MUR or PJD themselves, but adherence to the general Islamic norm of fasting the month of Ramadan is expected

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Similar to above, not mandated by the MUR or PJD themselves, but as members are assumed to be pious Muslims they are expected to keep halal

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: The PJD does not exert coercion on the matter, but as an Islamist group, members would be socially expected to perform the obligatory prayers (salat) five times daily

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 4

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50

Notes: Gatherings of the Friday afternoon prayer vary considerably depending on the demographic context and size(s) of mosque(s), really anywhere from a couple dozen to hundreds, not all of whom would fit inside

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: Attending Friday afternoon prayer at a mosque is seen as more obligatory than every prayer, five times daily, however some pious Muslims (including PJD membership) might choose to demonstrate their piety through more frequent attendance

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of

governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

Notes: The Moroccan state (less so the PJD) has been keen to promote the Maliki preferred practice of praying with arms at one's sides, rather than folded in front, but there is little indication of coercion on this matter

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Patterned, verbal responses to imam's sermon, recitation of the Fatiha (opening chapter of the Qur'an)

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence from eating pork and consuming alcohol; preference for halal verified meats

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Headscarf for women is more or less standard PJD dress code (as a normative marker of female piety for many other Muslims)

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Use of stock phrases referencing God, or other Qur'anic phrases in daily speech

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: "Brother" and "sister" are commonly used amongst like-minded, pious Muslim peers, though in Morocco in particular these forms of address are common much more widely. People may thus signal piety by using a more formal register of brother/sister than is common in Moroccan dialect.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Both MUR and PJD have formal institutional structures and internal elections.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: PJD candidates run for elections and hold political office in Moroccan parliament

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: Even when the PJD is in governmental power, the military and police force operate separately and, some say, are more closely aligned with the palace

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Most of Morocco's legal system is based on a common law system inherited from the French. However, family law (marriage, divorce, inheritance, etc.) is subject to a Personal Status Code, known as the Mudawwana, which is in principle based on Islamic legal doctrine of the Maliki school of law.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Moroccan public education system is primarily in standard Arabic, although some schools continue to use French for STEM fields.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A distinct dialect of Arabic known as darija is the most widely spoken language, while standard Arabic, French and English are taught in schools. Because Arabic is the language of the Qur'an, preferential use of a mix of darija laced with Qur'anic and other religious phrases would not necessarily index PJD membership but certainly an alignment with many of its values.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Islam of course has its own lunar calendar but this is not specific to the PJD. Like the Moroccan government, the PJD adheres to a mix of the lunar (hijri) calendar for religious functions and standard, Gregorian calendar for many other matters.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: As a social service organization, the MUR (social branch of the PJD) does provide food as a form of charity, but receipt is not necessarily based on membership in, or any formal relationship with the organization.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

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General References

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